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Gross Hematuria: Recurrent Phosphate Staghorn Calculi in a Healthy Adult - A Case Report

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Abstract:

Staghorn calculi are large renal stones that fill the pelvis of the kidney and pose a significant risk of urosepsis and intrinsic kidney damage. In this case, a 25-year-old healthy female presented with gross hematuria after vigorous cardiovascular exercise for six months. Computed tomography scan demonstrated a 5.4 cm right sided staghorn calculi with hydronephrosis. Right sided percutaneous nephrolithotomy followed by ureteroscopy was performed to remove the stone. On follow up ultrasound 3.5 weeks later, a 16 mm conglomerate of calculi was reformed in the lower calyx, requiring a second ureteroscopy for resolution. Nephrology workup for stone etiology was complicated because the patient did not maintain a stone free period for the gold standard 48 hour urine collection.

The case emphasizes a complete workup of gross hematuria, even in healthy young adults and to acknowledge exercise induced hematuria is a diagnosis of exclusion after complete workup for other causes. It highlights the gap in knowledge on staghorn calculi, likely due to the fewer number of cases per year despite the stone free rates for after staghorn calculi surgery being only 42%. There is need for better analysis as the current standard (48 hour urine collection) requires stone free periods that some patients, such as this one, may not be able to maintain and ultimately delay diagnosis and require more surgical procedures and medical risks.

BACKGROUND

Staghorn calculi are a less common type of kidney stone that are defined by filling the pelvis, infundibulum, and most calyces of the kidney. While common kidney stones are composed of calcium oxalate, staghorn calculi are typically composed of magnesium-ammonium-phosphate (MAP) and form secondary to recurrent urinary tract infections (UTIs). These stones make up about 4% of cases of nephrolithiasis and 85% of the cases of nephrolithiasis with gross hematuria (3). Typically, these stones are symptomatic with most common symptoms being flank pain, recurrent dysuria, and gross hematuria.

Treatment of staghorn calculi is a multi-faceted approach with the initial goal of removing the stone burden and a secondary goal of preventing urinary tract infections to decrease stone recurrence. The importance of surgery is pivotal as removing the stone requires careful planning and some urgency due to the risk of hydronephrosis, intrinsic kidney tissue damage, and urosepsis.

Per EAU, percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) remains the gold standard surgical technique. Surgical planning is mapped out with computed tomography (CT) scan and preoperative urine culture for antibiotic prophylaxis determination (1). In a study on PCNL vs open surgical approach, PCNL was associated with significantly shorter operative time (127 vs 204 minutes), shorter hospital stays, and earlier return to work (4). Iqbal et al determined an initial stone free rate of 42% in patients who underwent PCNL surgery (2). Stone free rate is critical to patients with recurrent kidney stones as rapid reaccumulating leads to risk for increased surgeries, surgical risks, and infection. Stone reaccumulation is highly related to residual fragments left in the kidney after operation as it provides a nidus for stone reformation. Shock wave lithotripsy and flexible ureteroscopy should be considered for repeat interventions to remove small stone debris and residual fragments.

After surgical removal, all specimens should be sent for stone analysis to determine the etiology of the

stone. Commonly, magnesium-ammonium-phosphate (MAP) stones are related to urinary tract infections (UTIs) and prophylactic antibiotics can be provided for prevention. However, there is a smaller subset of staghorn calculi formers which are not due to urinary tract infections. A study from 2017-2018 analyzed 190 patients who underwent PCNL for stones >2cm in size. 45% of these patients were diagnosed with a metabolic stone (4). Metabolic stones indicate an underlying problem such as hyperparathyroidism, renal tubular acidosis, and other metabolic and catabolic conditions. These stone fragments are typically made of calcium oxalate monohydrate or dihydrate and/or calcium phosphate (4).

The pertinent question lies in determining the risk for non-infection staghorn stones. These non-infectious stones typically have higher rates of rapid reaccumulation and pose higher health risks to the patient. Winoker et al. evaluated 25 patients with staghorn renal stones with no infection and compared to 64 usual staghorn stones (infection stones) and found hyperoxaluria was significantly higher in patients with no infection (4). Authors concluded that it is not clear why some metabolic stones assume staghorn configuration. Although potentially driven by urinary oxalate, whether a metabolic stone will form into a staghorn or not does not appear significantly influenced by more common causes of stone formation. Further work is needed to tease out the pathophysiology that drives the pathogenesis of this increasingly prevalent entity.

Given the lack of knowledge as to what increases the risk for staghorn calculi, all patients should undergo workup after stone removal in addition to stone analysis. This should include the gold standard, a 24 hour urine collection. It should be performed in 2-24 hour collections under typical diets and normal conditions (1). These patients should be stone free for at least 20 days (1), which poses difficulties for those with rapid stone reaccumulation. The results should be paired with lab work including PTH, CBC, and CMP.

CASE PRESENTATION

The patient is a healthy 25-year-old female presenting with 6 months of gross hematuria after exercise. She reported that consistently for 6 months she would get one to two episodes of gross hematuria after strenuous exercise such as running or cycling. She delayed presentation with the assumption that her symptoms were due to exercise induced hematuria, a benign condition common with strenuous exercise.

She denied dysuria or any gross hematuria at rest. She also denied any frothy or foamy appearing urine and any other changes to urine color outside of the red. She denied any UTI history except for one UTI when she was around 8 years old.

She reported her first kidney stone at age 17, diagnosed from ultrasound and passed spontaneously. She then had two more stones by the age of 21, both which passed on their own without surgical or medical interventions. She has been asymptomatic regarding kidney stones for 4 years prior to presentation. She has no other medical history and takes no relevant medications except for daily oral contraceptive pills. She is a never smoker, alcohol use twice yearly, and no illicit drug use. She is a current medical student completing her fourth year of medical school. Family history is notable for kidney stones on both sides of her family with a maternal uncle having a staghorn calculus as well.

She presented to her primary care physician where initial urinalysis was significant for microscopic and gross hematuria along with mild proteinuria. Given her symptoms, a non-contrast CT scan was performed, revealing complete staghorn calculus filling almost every calyx in the right kidney with mild upper pole hydronephrosis (Image 1). Total size of the stone was 5.4 cm with Hounsfield Units at 1300 Units indicating significant stone density. She was referred to urology specialists for definitive surgical management options and plans for nephrology work pending stone analysis.

INTERVENTIONS AND COURSE CONTINUED

Initial Surgical Intervention: Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy and Uteroscopy

Options of PCNL vs shock wave lithotripsy and ureteroscopy were weighed, but ultimately given the high stone burden, density, and desire for stone free status in a young patient, right sided PCNL surgery was decided. Open surgery was not recommended as PCNL is associated with significantly shorter operative time, hospital stays, return to work time (3). Pre-op labs were within normal limits and the patient received ampicillin and gentamicin antibiotics prior to surgery. PCNL surgery for stone removal was completed. The surgery required a 350 micron laser with 0.5 joule and 50 Hz lithotripsy to break up additional fragments before removing them with the basket. A right sided 6-French 24 cm urethral stent was placed. 2 weeks after this surgery, a ureteroscopy was performed to remove remaining stone debris and remove the stent without complications. Stone analysis was also sent and resulted in 100% calcium phosphate.

Follow up: Ultrasound

On follow up ultrasound, 3.5 weeks after the ureteroscopy, the ultrasound suggested the patient had regrown stones with CT confirming conglomerate formation up to size of 16 mm in the lower pole and two 2 mm stones in the upper pole.

Recurrent Surgical Intervention: Uteroscopy

Due to concern for rapid stone reaccumulation and lack of stone free period for at least twenty days, repeat surgical intervention was recommended. Right sided ureteroscopy was performed one month later, with the same protocol and pre-op procedure as the prior procedure. Uteroscopy was reassuring as the accumulation in the lower pole appeared to be calcified mucus that was removed via tobacco syringe to aspirate and clear the mucus. A basket plucked the new stones in the upper calyx and sent for repeat stone analysis. 200 micron laser

lithotripsy was performed to remove additional stone debris. 6 French x 24 cm ureteral stent was placed and stent removal was completed four days post-op without complication.

Limitations and Roadblocks' to Diagnoses:

The most crucial investigation is the 48 hour urine collection to determine the root cause of calcium phosphate stone formation in this patient. Given the lack of past medical history, urinary tract infections, or noted anatomical abnormalities on surgical intervention or imaging, the etiology of the stone is critical to prevention in the future. In order to perform 48 hour urine collection, some studies recommend at least twenty days of stone free period, which this patient has been unable to achieve.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSES OF STONE ETIOLOGIES

- **Anatomic Causes:** Ureterovesical Junction (UJ) strictures or acute angles at the UJ could challenge the flow of urine through the kidney, causing pooling of urine and creating a nidus for stone formation. Similarly, strictures of the ureters could cause a similar pathology. This was ruled out based on initial PCNL surgery where the surgeon examined the anatomy and determined no strictures from imaging or intraoperative fluoroscopy.
- **Infectious Causes:** Most common, staghorn calculi are caused by UTIs and stone analysis shows a mix of Magnesium-Ammonium-Phosphate. This patient stone was pure phosphate on all samples of the 5.4cm stone. Unlikely that the sample did not catch any of these other substances, and the patient lacks a history of UTIs.
- **Metabolic Causes:** Hyperparathyroidism, renal tubular acidosis type IV (RTA IV) are causes of phosphate kidney stones. However, metabolic stones would be expected not to spare one kidney. This patient had a clean left kidney and was only experiencing stone formation on the right

kidney. Without any other stigmata of hyperparathyroidism and lack of stones on the other kidney, metabolic stones seemed less plausible.

- Overall, the presence of the stones on one side only favored an anatomic cause, which was potentially ruled out by the surgeon. The composition of the stone leaned towards a metabolic etiology but without stones on the other kidney and lack of 24 hour urine collection, the stone cause remained unclear.

TREATMENT GOALS

Surgical Management Summary:

Management of staghorn calculus requires surgery as the standard of care given the risk for urosepsis and compromised kidney function. Protocol per *EAU Guidelines. Edn* (figure 1) was followed. In this patient, PCNL was an appropriate option for the initial management of the stone and follow up ultrasound was warranted to check for stone recurrence. The regrowth of the stone in 3.5 weeks was found to be more concerning for calcified mucus in the lower pole but still showed 2 stone formations of 2 mm each in the upper pole requiring repeat surgical intervention.

Stone Workup:

The gold standard for kidney stone etiology is stone analysis which was performed in the initial PCNL surgery. The stone analysis yielded 100% calcium phosphate. To determine the cause of a 100% phosphate based stone, a 48 hour urine collection was recommended by nephrology, but the patient has not had a stone free period to complete the urine collection studies. Therefore, her course becomes complicated by a cycle of surgical interventions without proper workup of the cause of the stones in the first place. Etiology and therefore treatment for phosphate stones can be followed by *EAU Guidelines. Edn* (figure 2) for prevention and medical management.

OUTCOME AND FOLLOW-UP

After stent removal from the second ureteroscopy, the patient remains in good health. She continues to complete her fourth year of medical school, exercise without episodes of hematuria, and is pain free. She is back to her baseline activities and abilities. She will continue to follow with nephrology and urology for medical and surgical prevention and monitoring. Currently, the patient has no stone burden with the last ureteroscopy and will require ultrasound follow up in 3 months, which if stone free at this time, can allow for 48 hour urine collection work up.

The priority remains to identify the cause of the calcium phosphate stone. There is more reassurance given that the second stone accumulation appeared to be more calcified mucus as opposed to rapid stone re-accumulation. However, this does not take away from the fact that without diagnoses, there is still risk for further surgical interventions. The goal is to limit surgical interventions given the four surgical procedures required over the last six months.

Additional measures in the meantime include emphasis on increased hydration of 2.5-3 L a day with a goal of 2-2.5L of urine output each day. Dietary modifications and focus on low salt were recommended. Lastly, percussion/reverberation in reverse Trendelenburg two-three times weekly has some support for benefits in breaking stones and preventing stasis specifically in the lower poles of the kidney to promote stone clearance.

DISCUSSION

Staghorn calculi represent a small (4%) of cases of nephrolithiasis, but pose larger medical complications and surgical interventions (3). Staghorn stones typically are composed of MAP and are related to recurrent UTIs. However, a smaller percentage of cases are due to underlying metabolic or anatomic etiologies including ureter strictures, hyperparathyroidism, and renal tubular acidosis amongst others. The current gold standard workup includes urinalysis, CT scan and

percutaneous nephrolithotomy for surgical removal of stone burden. PCNL is shown to have the best outcomes in terms of lower stone recurrence rates (2) using a minimally invasive approach with less hospitalization days, rates of transfusions, and postoperative complications.

In evaluation of previously healthy females who present with the only symptom being gross hematuria after vigorous exercise, a full workup is required. While rates of staghorn are low, there are complications that come with these stones. In this case, the patient, a healthy 25 year old female, presumed she had exercise induced hematuria, as this is most common in her demographic and history. However, delay in seeking care likely contributed to her building stone burden. Strong precautions and primary care encouragement for seeking evaluation should be prioritized. This highlights the importance of a thorough review of systems when encountering patients, as many patients will fail to report their symptoms unless directly asked.

As highlighted in this case, staghorn stones may be due to other causes outside of infections. This patient had a stone analysis that showed 100% calcium phosphate composition. The gap in the literature is apparent in this patient case, as she has a high stone recurrence rate requiring 4 procedures and failing to have a stone free period for more than twenty days in a 6 month period (1). This inhibits her ability to have an accurate 24 hour urine collection for evaluation of why she developed staghorn calculi. Therefore, further research into common causes of metabolic staghorn stone formation and better techniques outside of 24 hour urine collection for those with rapid stone recurrence. Without these interventions, patients with rapid stone recurrence are subjected to increased numbers of surgeries which comes with its own risks not limited to infection, transfusions, and post surgical complications.

This case highlights multiple aspects of care including the reminder to keep a broad differential diagnosis, prioritize throughout review of systems, and the gaps in knowledge and management of

staghorn calculi with metabolic stone etiology and further work that should be done to prioritize patient outcomes and underlying stone etiology analysis. The patient in this case reports remains without answers. Attempts at prevention with percussion/verbnation therapy will be attempted, but no definite cause and method of prevention has been identified to date for this patient's stones (5).

LEARNING POINTS/ TAKE HOME MESSAGES

- Encouraging prompt presentation for gross hematuria is key. Delays in care lead to increased risk for stone accumulation and staghorn formation, urosepsis, and intrinsic kidney damage along with challenges for surgical repair
- Thorough evaluation of all gross hematuria, regardless of age should be done. Exercise induced hematuria is a diagnosis of exclusion and should not be assumed unless thorough workup and rule out of other conditions, including staghorn calculi is done.
- Rates of stone re-accumulation and staghorn formation are not fully understood and it is unclear why some individuals seem more prone to staghorn than others.
- There are gaps in the literature regarding metabolic stone and stone formation rate and lack proper testing as urine collection studies require twenty day stone free periods which can be challenging for some patients.
- Further research into metabolic stone and staghorn calculi need to be done to optimize management and minimize repeat operations.

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